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If you reflect a mirror in the in the correct spots of the last supper, you will see where Leonard Da Vinci hid the word Omega. He has hidden dragons in probably all of his paintings, and the Vetruvian man "stands for" Omega.un=o/vv= m/e/tri=g/a. The goat lives on in me.

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